

1 **Title:** Assessment of solar photo-Fenton, photocatalysis, and H₂O₂ for removal of
2 phytopathogen fungi spores in synthetic and real effluents of urban wastewater.

3
4
5 **Authors:** Polo-López M.I., Castro-Alfárez M., Oller, I., Fernández-Ibáñez P.*

6
7 Plataforma Solar de Almería –CIEMAT, P.O. Box 22, 04200 Tabernas, Almería, Spain.

8
9 Authors email list:

10 inmaculada.polo@psa.es

11 maria.castro@psa.es

12 isabel.oller@psa.es

13 pilar.fernandez@psa.es

14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24 ***CORRESPONDING AUTHOR:**

25 Dr. Pilar Fernández-Ibáñez

26 Plataforma Solar de Almería – CIEMAT, PO Box 22, 04200 Tabernas, Almería, Spain

27 Phone: + 34 950 387957

28 Fax: + 34 950 363015

29 Email: pilar.fernandez@psa.es

1 **Abstract**

2 Scarcity of fresh water is a major environmental problem, and properly treated
3 wastewater could be an alternative renewable water resource, especially for agriculture as
4 the final point-of-use. But before wastewater can be reused, it must be treated to meet
5 chemical and biological quality standards, which depend on the final use and legislation.
6 Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs) have been demonstrated to be very efficient in
7 decreasing the pathogen load in contaminated water. This study presents the experimental
8 evaluation of several solar-driven AOPs, i.e., photo-Fenton (Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+}) at low reagent
9 concentration, heterogeneous photocatalysis (TiO_2), and solar photoassisted H_2O_2
10 treatment for removal of the spores of *Fusarium* sp, a worldwide phytopathogen. The
11 experimental work was done in a pilot solar photoreactor with compound parabolic
12 collectors (CPC). Disinfection of *Fusarium solani* spores by all treatments was excellent
13 in distilled water and in simulated municipal wastewater effluent (SMWWE).
14 Degradation of dissolved organic carbon (DOC) was also evaluated. The inactivation
15 rates varied depending on the water matrix, and disinfection was fastest in distilled water
16 followed by SMWWE. The best *F. solani* inactivation rate was with photo-Fenton
17 treatment (10/20 mg/L of $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$) at pH 3, followed by $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{Solar}$ (10 mg/L) and
18 finally $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Solar}$ was the slowest. These results underline the importance of solar AOPs
19 and the CPC reactor technology as a good option for waterborne pathogen removal.

20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29

30 **Keywords:** *Fusarium* sp, Compound Parabolic Collector, Photo-Fenton, Solar radiation,
31 Titanium dioxide, Wastewater reuse.

1 **1. Introduction**

2 Reuse of wastewater is currently one of the strongest alternative solutions for
3 water scarcity [1], and the need to make use of this resource is constantly increasing due
4 to urban, industrial and agricultural water pollution [1]. Reuse for agriculture is of special
5 interest, because according to the FAO, it is the largest fresh water consumer [2]. Scarcity
6 of fresh water sources, biological contamination of water, and soil salinization affect food
7 production worldwide. To save water, especially where there is a salinity problem and/or
8 water sources are scarce, hydroponic agriculture could be a solution, as plants are grown
9 in a recirculating nutrient solution instead of soil, thereby reducing the water requirement
10 and making use of land lost to salinization. In addition, it can also make use of water
11 from properly treated wastewater effluents [3]. However, before waste water can be used,
12 any pathogens must be removed, because this is one of the most common ways that
13 diseases are spread in hydroponic crops. The largest group of pathogens is the fungi,
14 which also produce the most diseases in plants. The pathogen load in water reclaimed for
15 irrigation must therefore be reduced to decrease the incidence of crop diseases and health
16 risk to agricultural products [4].

17 Traditional techniques used to eliminate pathogens from water do not always
18 ensure complete disinfection. Chemical pesticides, fungicides, etc., increase pollution of
19 soil and fresh water and are often ineffective. The use of chlorine has been restricted
20 because of its generation of hazardous trihalomethane by-products in the presence of
21 organic matter, and other traditional chemical fungicides, such as etridiazol, are known to
22 become phytotoxic [5]. On the other hand, interest of researchers in new water treatment
23 techniques like the Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs) has increased in the last few
24 decades. These processes have been widely studied since the 60s [6]. AOPs generate
25 oxidizing species (especially OH^{*}) which attack organic chemical compounds, often
26 completely mineralizing them into CO₂ and H₂O [7]. Research on the degradation of
27 hazardous chemical compounds in water by AOPs, and in particular, photo-Fenton and
28 titanium dioxide (TiO₂) using natural solar radiation, should be highlighted [6]. The
29 effectiveness of this technology is especially enhanced by the solar reactors used. AOPs
30 in Compound Parabolic Collector (CPC) reactors have been demonstrated to be highly
31 efficient for removing chemical compounds and pathogens from water [6,8]. The

1 effectiveness of solar photo-Fenton and TiO₂ has been shown for several kinds of
2 microorganisms, spores of fungi like *Fusarium* spp (a large genus of filamentous soil
3 fungi found in water systems worldwide, including reservoirs, rivers, coastal seawater,
4 wastewater effluents, and even hospital water distribution systems [9,10,11]), and
5 bacteria like *E. coli* [12,13].

6 Titanium dioxide is one of the most widely studied photocatalysts. It is a
7 semiconductor particle, which when photoexcited by photons at $\lambda < 385$ nm in water in
8 the presence of oxygen, generates superoxide ions (O₂^{•-}) and hydroxyl radicals (OH[•])
9 [14].

10 More recently, research on photo-Fenton for water disinfection has increased due
11 to its high potential for producing OH[•] radicals at acid pH (optimum for Fenton reaction
12 2.8). This system consists of generating OH[•] through the catalytic cycle of iron ions
13 (Fe²⁺) combined with H₂O₂ irradiated by UV-Vis up to a wavelengths of 600 nm [15]:

17
18 An alternative to the above mentioned solar AOPs is solar photo-assisted H₂O₂
19 (H₂O₂/Solar). This process has recently shown good inactivation efficiencies using less
20 than toxic H₂O₂ concentrations to remove microorganisms like bacteria and fungi in
21 water [11,12,16,17].

22 This article reports on the efficiency of solar-driven photo-Fenton with Fe²⁺ and
23 Fe³⁺, TiO₂ and H₂O₂/sunlight in a 60-L CPC reactor for inactivating spores of *Fusarium*
24 *solani* in distilled water (DW) and simulated municipal wastewater effluent (SMWWE).

25 26 **2. Materials and methods**

27 **2.1 Compound Parabolic Collector (CPC) solar reactor**

28 The CPC solar photo-reactor (Figure 1a) used for all experiments is described
29 elsewhere [10,11]. It consists of two CPC mirror modules, with 20 borosilicate-glass
30 tubes. The total irradiated collector surface is 4.5 m² and the illuminated water volume is
31 45 L over a total volume of 60 L. The flow rate is set at 30 L/min for turbulent flow

1 (Reynolds = 16,600). pH, dissolved oxygen, and temperature were continuously
2 monitored and recorded by software.

3 4 **2.2 Enumeration and quantification of *Fusarium solani* spores**

5 *F. solani* was isolated from samples taken in the Andarax River in Almería,
6 Spain, as described elsewhere [9,10,11]. Spores were counted using the pour plate
7 technique by spreading 50, 250, 500 μ L in acidified malt agar (Panreac, Spain). Spore
8 concentration is expressed as colony forming units per milliliter (CFU/mL). The
9 quantification method detection limit (DL) is 2(\pm 2) CFU/mL. Three replicates were done
10 of all samples and treatments. For real wastewater experiments, all naturally occurring
11 fungi (so-named ‘other fungi’ in Figure 7b) present in the effluent were detected and
12 enumerated using same growing media and culture protocol as that used for *Fusarium*.
13 These water samples were plated without any dilution and the DL was the same.

14 15 **2.3 Solar treatments**

16 All experiments were conducted in triplicate at the PSA under natural solar
17 radiation on completely sunny days and lasted 5 h. The results of the three replicates were
18 highly reproducible. The average of the results is reported along with an error equal to the
19 standard deviation. Reactor tank was filled with 60L of either distilled water, or synthetic
20 WW effluent, or real WW effluent, for each type of experiment. In all cases, *Fusarium*
21 suspension and reagents were added to the CPC reactor water and recirculated in the dark
22 for 15 min (homogenization time). After that, the reactor was uncovered and 10-mL
23 samples were taken during the experiment for spore and reagent quantification. The first
24 sample was used to determine the starting spore concentration and as a control, and
25 therefore, it was kept in the dark at 25°C and re-plated again at the end of the experiment.
26 Fungal regrowth (48 h) was also evaluated at the end of the experiment, and no regrowth
27 was found in water samples when the DL was reached.

28 For the case of synthetic effluents disinfection, the following solar runs were
29 done: (i) H₂O₂/sunlight (10 mg/L); (ii) TiO₂/sunlight (100 mg/L); (iii) photo-Fenton at pH
30 8, with Fe²⁺/H₂O₂: 5/10 mg/L; (iv) photo-Fenton at pH 3 with Fe²⁺/H₂O₂: 5/10 mg/L and
31 10/20 mg/L, same photo-Fenton tests with additional H₂O₂ dosing to avoid limitation of

1 photo-Fenton reactions by lack of H_2O_2 , therefore the minimum H_2O_2 concentration was
2 above 2 mg/L during the treatment in all cases; (v) photo-Fenton at pH3 with $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$:
3 5/10 mg/L and 10/20 mg/L, and same photo-Fenton tests with similar H_2O_2 adding.

4 For the case of real effluents disinfection, the following solar runs were done: (i)
5 H_2O_2 /sunlight (10 mg/L) with adding of 60 mg/L (6 times 10 mg/L to maintain the level
6 of H_2O_2 in the water); (ii) TiO_2 /sunlight (100 mg/L); (iii) photo-Fenton at pH 3, with
7 $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$: 5/10 mg/L with additional H_2O_2 dosing of 50 mg/L.

9 **2.4 Types of water**

10 Distilled water was used as a model water to study inactivation behavior in
11 absence of organic and inorganic salts. The simulated municipal wastewater effluent
12 (SMWWE), which avoided fluctuation in Dissolved Organic Matter (DOC) generated by
13 the microbiological load and the chemical compound variability of real MWWE, was the
14 complex water. SMWWE with 25 mg/L of DOC was used as the wastewater effluent
15 model. The same kind of simulated wastewater effluent has been used elsewhere [11,17].

16 Real effluents from a municipal wastewater treatment plant in Almería were
17 freshly collected for the experiments (RMWWE). This effluent proceeds from a
18 secondary treatment, i.e. activated sludge treatment followed by sedimentation in settling
19 ponds. RWWE had an average DOC of 16.5 mg/L, dissolved inorganic carbon of 72
20 mg/L, turbidity of 8.5 NTU, pH 7.6, and conductivity 1790 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$.

22 **2.5 Reagents**

23 H_2O_2 (30 wt%, Riedel-de-Haën, Germany) was used as received and diluted
24 directly in the reactor water. The H_2O_2 concentration was measured during the solar
25 experiment by a colorimetric method with Titanium (IV) oxysulphate (Riedel-de-Haën,
26 Germany) [11,16].

27 Ferrous sulphate heptahydrate ($\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Panreac, Spain) and ferric nitrate
28 ($\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Panreac, Spain) were used as the sources of Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} , respectively.
29 Iron concentration was determined with 1.10 phenanthroline according to ISO 6332. The
30 mg/L iron to H_2O_2 concentration ratio was 1:2.

1 TiO₂ Aeroxide P25 particles (Evonick, Degussa Corp., Germany) were used as
2 received from the manufacturer. The powder was diluted in a small volume of water and
3 then added to the reactor to form a homogeneous suspension.

4 5 **2.6 Solar radiation**

6 A global UVA pyranometer (295–385 nm, Model CUV4, Kipp & Zonen,
7 Netherlands) tilted 37 degrees was used to measure UV irradiance (in W/m²) during the
8 experiments. As the experiments were conducted on different days, to compare results,
9 the inactivation kinetics was evaluated as a function of cumulative energy per unit of
10 volume (Q_{UV} , kJ/L) received in the photo-reactor [8]. Q_{UV} is commonly used to compare
11 results under different conditions as calculated by Equation 3:

$$12 \quad Q_{uv,n} = Q_{uv,n-1} + \Delta t_n UV_{G,n} A_r / V_t; \Delta t_n = t_n - t_{n-1} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

13
14 where $Q_{uv,n}$ and $Q_{uv,n-1}$ is the cumulative UV energy per liter (kJ/L) at times n and $n-1$;
15 $UV_{G,n}$ is the average incident radiation on the irradiated area (W/m²), Δt_n is the
16 experimental time of sample (s), A_r is the illuminated area of collector (m²), and V_t is
17 the total volume of water treated (L).

18
19 All experiments started at the same local time and lasted 5 hours in consecutive
20 days, so that water temperature and solar UVA irradiance was similar between different
21 solar tests. The average solar UVA irradiance during all the experiments was 35.3(±1.2)
22 W/m², with maximum and minimum values of 28.2(±1.2) W/m² and 49.1(±2.0) W/m²,
23 respectively (Figure 1b). The typical solar spectrum recorded in the location of the
24 experiments during one of these days is also presented (inset of Figure 1b).

25 26 **2.7 Kinetics reaction**

27 The inactivation kinetics of the different treatments was calculated using the Q_{UV}
28 parameter instead of the duration of the experiment. For this purpose Chick's law was
29 adjusted to the photo-chemical results using the solar UVA energy received in the photo-
30 reactor (Q_{UV}) which also takes time into account (see Eq. 3)[8]:

1

$$\text{Log}\left(\frac{N}{N_0}\right) = -k' \cdot Q_{UV} \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

2 where N/N_0 is the reduction in spore concentration, k' is the disinfection kinetic rate, and
3 Q_{UV} is the solar UVA energy received in the photo-reactor.

4

5 **3. Results and Discussion**

6 **3.1 Spore inactivation by H₂O₂/Solar**

7 Figure 2 shows the inactivation kinetics of *F. solani* spores in DW and SMWWE
8 with 10 mg/L of H₂O₂ added. The detection limit was reached in DW with a cumulative
9 solar UV irradiance of 13.3 kJ/L. In SMWWE, a similar result required 18.9 kJ/L of Q_{UV} .
10 pH did not show change significantly and remained at 6.7 and 8 in DW and SMWWE,
11 respectively. DOC in SMWWE is shown in Figure 2, where no significant reduction
12 (2 %) is observed.

13 Previous findings have shown *Fusarium* spp spore susceptibility to the synergistic
14 killing effect of H₂O₂/Solar. Sichel et al. demonstrated that addition of H₂O₂ at low
15 concentrations (5-500 mg/L) could enhance the inactivation effect of solar-only
16 disinfection, while similar concentrations in the dark did not have any negative effect on
17 spore viability [16]. *F. equiseti* chlamydospores were also found to be susceptible to
18 inactivation with 10 mg/L H₂O₂ and solar radiation, achieving higher inactivation kinetics
19 in DW than in SMWWE [11]. Results of our study were similar for *F. solani*
20 microconidia, where inactivation efficiency was higher in DW than SMMWE. This could
21 be because, the diffusion of H₂O₂ inside cells in absence of any chemical compound may
22 be faster than in presence of organic matter, which under certain conditions, is known to
23 react with H₂O₂ to form disinfection by-products (DBPs) [18]. Therefore, the H₂O₂
24 reaction with organic matter in SMWWE could cause lower fungi inactivation kinetics
25 than in DW.

26 The inactivation mechanism of this treatment has also been described in the
27 literature for bacteria like *E. coli* [12], *Salmonella* and coliforms [19], and for fungi
28 spores [11]. This mechanism is based on the H₂O₂ diffusion inside cells, reacting with the

1 free iron (labile iron pool) present inside them, and generating OH[•] by reactions similar to
2 photo-Fenton (Eq. 1-2), which damage internal structures and finally lead to cell death.

4 **3.2 Spore inactivation by TiO₂/Solar**

5 Solar photocatalytic experiments were conducted using 100 mg/L of TiO₂
6 Aeroxide P25 slurry catalyst. The best conditions for TiO₂ suspensions in the 60-L CPC
7 photo-reactor for similar fungi strains have previously been reported to be 100 mg/L [10].
8 To achieve complete spore inactivation, 31.8 kJ/L of Q_{UV} were required (Figure 3), and
9 DOC was reduced 56% at the end of the experimental time with 55.42 kJ/L of Q_{UV} . The
10 highest temperature was 44.1°C and pH was almost constant at 7.8.

11 The microorganism inactivation efficiency by TiO₂ with solar energy has been
12 widely studied during the last decades for bacteria to cancer cells [6,19], including
13 *Fusarium* sp spores in a 200-mL solar bottle reactor [9], a 14-L CPC photoreactor [8] and
14 60-L CPC photoreactor [10].

15 Inactivation strongly depends on the OH[•] radicals generated during photocatalysis.
16 First the cell wall is attacked and then cell integrity is disrupted, leading to cell death
17 [20]. Irradiated TiO₂ surfaces react with intermediate hydroperoxide, initiating cascades
18 of autoxidation reactions [21]. The formation of peroxidation products such as aldehydes,
19 ketones, and carboxylic acids at the same time as cell wall membrane constituents
20 disappear has been reported in the literature [21]. Fungi inactivation kinetics could be
21 enhanced by the formation of aggregates of catalyst and microorganisms, allowing attack
22 by OH[•] generated directly on the microorganism cell wall. This effect has been well
23 documented in *Fusarium* sp spores by direct observation of the aggregates formed during
24 the experiments [10]. On the other hand, chemicals like carbonates and bicarbonates in
25 water limit the photocatalytic reaction, as they act as OH[•] scavengers [22]. SMWWE
26 contains approximately 17 mg/L of Inorganic Carbon (IC) at pH8, which could diminish
27 the efficiency of the photocatalytic treatment. However, these results showed good spore
28 inactivation and DOC degradation even in their presence.

31 **3.3 Spore inactivation by photo-Fenton (Fe²⁺ or Fe³⁺) in distilled water.**

1 Figure 4a shows spore inactivation by photo-Fenton with different $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$
2 concentrations, (5/10 and 10/20 mg/L, respectively). H_2O_2 dosing during the solar
3 treatment was also evaluated. pH was not adjusted to optimum (pH 2.8) to avoid any
4 chemical modification in the water matrix. Table 1 shows H_2O_2 consumption, pH, Fe^{2+} ,
5 Fe^{3+} and total iron (Fe^{T}) measured during the experiments. Dissolved iron measured
6 during the experiment was almost the total starting amount, and high iron loss due to
7 precipitation at neutral pH was not observed. The detection limit (DL) was reached in all
8 cases. No significant differences were observed among the different test conditions. The
9 energy required to reach the DL varied from 26 to 29.5 kJ/L of Q_{UV} , with best results with
10 5 and 10 mg/L of $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ (Figure 4a). Therefore, in DW, neither the addition of H_2O_2
11 nor increasing iron concentration from 5 to 10 mg/L led to better microconidia
12 inactivation kinetics.

13 Similar conditions were evaluated using Fe^{3+} with inactivation results as shown in
14 Figure 4b. In all cases, the DL was met, and a slight enhancement of disinfection
15 efficiency was observed for 5/10 mg/L of $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$. On the other hand, no significant
16 improvement was achieved with higher iron concentrations (10/20 mg/L of $\text{Fe}^{3+}/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$).

17 Microorganism inactivation by solar photo-Fenton is the result of accumulated damage
18 done by the following simultaneous or sequential processes: (i) Reactive Oxygen Species
19 (ROS) generated by the direct action of sunlight, which mainly attack the DNA
20 molecules, generating cross links; (ii) the OH^{\bullet} generated by photo-Fenton reactions (Eq.
21 1-2), affecting mainly the integrity of the external cell wall of the spores.

22 Nevertheless, when inactivation results with 5 and 10 mg/L of Fe^{2+} or $3+$ are
23 compared, photo-Fenton inactivation with Fe^{2+} (26.5 kJ/L, in 3 hours) required less solar
24 UV-energy than Fe^{3+} (37.9 kJ/L, in 4 hours) (Fig. 4a and 4b). This difference can be
25 attributed to the different biological behavior of the iron depending on its speciation in
26 the water. In the literature, Fe^{2+} could reportedly cross biological membranes freely,
27 while Fe^{3+} could form exciplexes with organic compounds in the cell wall [12,23].
28 Therefore, Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} inactivation mechanisms may behave different. Fe^{2+} diffusion
29 inside cells may increase the inactivation efficiency by generating OH^{\bullet} which reacts with
30 metabolic H_2O_2 according to Eqs. 1-2, while Fe^{3+} may form complexes in the cell wall
31 where it causes damage. It should be remarked that the starting total dissolved iron (Fe^{T})

1 concentration of 5 mg/L remained nearly constant during the experiment for Fe^{2+} , while it
2 decreased from 4.73 to 1.89 mg/L for Fe^{3+} . This difference could also account for lower
3 OH^\bullet generation by Fe^{3+} than Fe^{2+} .

4 Inactivation of *F. solani* spores was not enhanced by increasing Fe^{2+} or Fe^{3+}
5 concentration from 5 to 10 mg/L, which is in agreement with previous findings [17]. This
6 is explained by precipitation of the iron in water. In both cases, high losses of the initial
7 iron added were observed. This is probably the reason why increasing iron over 5 mg/L
8 does not lead to significant improvement of spore inactivation efficacy. These results
9 show that regardless of how much iron is added at the beginning, it is the amount actually
10 dissolved that is important to photo-Fenton efficiency.

11 On the other hand, the tests with dosed H_2O_2 showed the same efficiency as those
12 without it. H_2O_2 dosing depended on consumption during solar treatment according to
13 Eq. 1. In this case, only was required the addition of a 10 mg/L dose of H_2O_2 during the
14 experiment which did not result in any enhancement in process efficiency (Fig. 4a).

15 16 **3.4 Spore inactivation by photo-Fenton (Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+}) in SMWWE.**

17 Spore inactivation was evaluated in SMWWE to study the effect of this water on
18 photo-Fenton efficiency. 5 and 10 mg/L of Fe^{2+} or Fe^{3+} combined with 10 and 20 mg/L of
19 H_2O_2 , respectively, and the effect of dosing H_2O_2 during the experiment were studied.
20 The DOC concentration was also measured during all tests. Data on pH, H_2O_2 and iron
21 concentration are shown in Table 2.

22 Figure 5a shows that all the photo-Fenton reagent combinations at pH 3 and
23 concentrations tested with Fe^{2+} reached the DL, except for natural pH (pH ~ 8). In that
24 case both spores and DOC concentrations remained almost constant during 5 hours of
25 solar exposure, and dissolved Fe^T concentration measured was 0 (Table 2), i.e., all the
26 iron added was precipitated and there was no iron available to produce oxidative damage
27 to spores.

28 Moreover, chemical species like carbonates/bicarbonates present in SMWWE
29 decrease process efficiency, as they scavenge radicals like OH^\bullet , and compete with other
30 organic contaminants for OH^\bullet . This also occurs with phosphate, sulphate, fluoride,
31 bromide and chloride, etc. [6]. Therefore, for the photo-Fenton assays, the pH of the

1 water was adjusted to ~3 (optimum for photo-Fenton [15]) for several reasons: i) spore
2 inactivation at pH8 was very poor; ii) the iron concentration was entirely precipitated; iii)
3 the viability of *Fusarium* sp spores was not affected at acid pH [17]; and iv) the
4 acidification of the solution also allows carbonates/bicarbonates to be eliminated as CO₂.

5 The detection limit was met with 5/10 and 10/20 mg/L of Fe²⁺/H₂O₂, with no
6 significant differences observed between those conditions, which required 20 and
7 18.9 kJ/L of Q_{UV} , respectively (Fig. 5a). Therefore, increased iron concentration did not
8 enhance spore inactivation efficiency. However, DOC was lowered more with 10 mg/L
9 of Fe²⁺ (75%) than with 5 mg/L (65%) (Fig. 5b).

10 The enhancement of inactivation kinetics by dosing H₂O₂, observed in all
11 SMWWE tests (Fig. 5b), was not observed in DW. In these experiments, H₂O₂ demand
12 was high, and therefore, the 10 mg/L doses had to be added every 30 minutes. Both spore
13 inactivation and DOC reduction were enhanced for 5 and 10 mg/L of Fe²⁺ with
14 continuous addition of H₂O₂. The best inactivation rate was achieved with 10 mg/L of
15 Fe²⁺, which required 8.4 kJ/L of Q_{UV} . At the end of the experiment, 83% DOC reduction
16 was obtained with a Q_{UV} of 44.8 kJ/L.

17 The pattern of spore inactivation kinetics with Fe³⁺ (Fig. 6a) was similar to Fe²⁺,
18 i.e., dosing of H₂O₂ during the experiment led to better spore inactivation results, and
19 increasing iron concentration from 5 to 10 mg/L did not significantly enhance them. DOC
20 degradation (Fig. 6b) was slightly better for 10 mg/L of iron, although no significant
21 difference was observed between the two cases.

22 Of the two iron salts, Fe²⁺ inactivation kinetics were better, requiring 8.4 kJ/L and
23 12.1 kJ/L of Q_{UV} for 10 and 5 mg/L of iron, respectively, and dosed H₂O₂, while the same
24 concentrations of Fe³⁺ needed 12.3 kJ/L and 13.9 kJ/L of Q_{UV} for the same inactivation.
25 On the contrary, DOC reduction was very similar in all cases. This means that
26 degradation of chemical compounds is not affected by the starting amount of iron salt
27 added to the photo-Fenton cycle.

28 Spore inactivation mechanisms are similar to those described in the previous
29 section. The direct action of sunlight, OH[•] generated by Eqs. 1-2 and OH[•] generated by
30 internal photo-Fenton reactions are mainly responsible for inactivation with Fe²⁺. In
31 SMWWE, the Fe³⁺ reaction with inorganic compounds like sulphates and chlorides may

1 reduce process efficiency. These inorganic compounds have been shown to reduce the
2 H₂O₂ decomposition rate for Fe³⁺/H₂O₂ in the dark. This effect is due to the formation of
3 Fe³⁺ complexes with the generation of less reactive (SO₄^{•-}) or much less reactive (Cl₂^{•-})
4 species [24]. Thus the presence of inorganic anions may affect iron reactivity, and can
5 also scavenge OH[•] radicals, producing less reactive inorganic radicals [24].

6 Water temperature can be also an important factor affecting inactivation
7 efficiency in SMWWE. Mild temperatures (from 25 to 45°C) may affect process
8 efficiency in different ways. Raising the temperature in this range increases the
9 disinfection rate, favoring spore germination, affecting distribution of iron and the H₂O₂
10 consumption rate in the photo-Fenton reaction. Very few studies have reported on the
11 effect of high temperatures (over 50°C) in the photo-Fenton reaction. Gernjak *et al.*
12 (2006) found that under certain conditions (maximal iron concentration 2.6 mM and
13 maximal temperature 70°C) the reaction rate increased about 5 times in terms of H₂O₂
14 consumption by increasing temperature from 20°C to 50°C, which did not affect the iron
15 concentration [25]. In view of the above considerations, the effect of increasing the
16 temperature required more H₂O₂ to be added during the dosing experiments, i.e., the
17 increased temperature determined that 10 mg/L doses of H₂O₂ had to be added every 30
18 minutes to maintain H₂O₂ concentration. The effect of the water matrix composition on
19 H₂O₂ demands was discarded because H₂O₂ demands in experiments performed with DW
20 at higher temperatures (data not shown) were also higher.

21 Total consumption of H₂O₂ for 5 and 10 mg/L of Fe²⁺ was 50 and 100 mg/L,
22 respectively, while 10 and 20 mg/L of H₂O₂ were consumed when no H₂O₂ was added. In
23 the experiments done with Fe³⁺, 70 and 140 mg/L of H₂O₂ were consumed during the
24 dosage experiments. Spore inactivation and DOC degradation were slightly enhanced
25 when H₂O₂ was added. DOC degradation became stationary where the optimized
26 photoreaction conditions did not lead directly to organic matter degradation
27 enhancement. This is because the organic matter present in the SMWWE consists mainly
28 of aliphatic compounds like carboxylic acids which are very difficult to degrade past a
29 certain percentage.

30 Table 3 shows the inactivation kinetics for SMWWE treatments. The highest
31 inactivation rate was found for photo-Fenton with Fe²⁺ (10 mg/L + dosed H₂O₂).

1 Nevertheless, there are no significant differences in inactivation rates among the
2 treatments.

3 Moreover, for solar treatment applications in the field, it should be taken into
4 account that the solar treatments studied require post-treatment (pH neutralization and
5 catalyst removal) before the treated wastewater can be reused. TiO₂ catalyst should be
6 removed from the treated water prior to reuse, for which sedimentation/flocculation and
7 filtration are necessary. For H₂O₂/solar, post-treatment is unnecessary if the reagent
8 concentration is below 50 mg/L (10 mg/L), as it is non-toxic for plants [16]. Moreover,
9 Bichai *et al.* demonstrated the ability of H₂O₂ (10 mg/L)/solar to disinfect real and
10 simulated MWWE contaminated by *E. coli*, and the treated WW was reused for lettuce
11 irrigating [26]. Small amounts of iron (~10 mg/L) should be used for photo-Fenton
12 treatments to meet water pollution control regulations (e.g., Spanish Royal Decree
13 849/1986, on Regulation of Water Pollution Control), and these amounts could also be
14 used as fertilizer. On the other hand, H₂O₂ concentrations added for photo-Fenton could
15 be neglected as it is consumed by the reactions. The major post-treatment of photo-
16 Fenton is neutralization of the pH, as low pH could damage plants.

17

18 **3.5 Spore inactivation by three solar AOPs in real MWWE**

19 For experimental validation of the capabilities of these solar AOPs for WW
20 disinfection, the following evaluation has been done in real MWWE. Figure 7 shows the
21 inactivation efficiency of solar/H₂O₂, TiO₂ at 100 mg/L, and photo-Fenton with ferrous
22 sulphate at Fe²⁺/H₂O₂: 5/10 mg/L at pH3. These experiments were done at natural pH (8)
23 except photo-Fenton, which was done at pH 3 to avoid iron precipitation. This
24 acidification induced carbonates/bicarbonates content removal from this WW (dissolved
25 inorganic carbon = 72 mg/L), which avoids any scavenging effect of these species for
26 hydroxyl radicals. *Fusarium* inactivation in RWWE (Fig. 7a) was very similar for the
27 three AOPs, reaching the DL at 27 kJ/L of Q_{UV} . Solar H₂O₂ and photo-Fenton in SMME
28 required shorter treatment times and lower Q_{UV} values to achieve similar results, while no
29 differences were observed when TiO₂ photocatalysis was employed.

30 Similarly to the results obtained with SMWWE, DOC was no reduced using
31 solar/H₂O₂. Regarding solar photocatalysis (TiO₂), DOC reduction in real effluents was

1 around 2% (data not shown), while in synthetic effluents this reduction was 55% (Figure
2 3). This may be attributed to the high complexity (chemical and biological) of real WW
3 effluents compared with synthetic ones. Photo-Fenton led to a 34% reduction in the
4 organic matter (data not shown). This DOC decrease is not very high because the effluent
5 proceeds from an activated sludge treatment and the chemical composition is based in
6 highly degraded/oxidized compounds.

7
8 The role of organic matter in water disinfection by AOPs remains still uncertain.
9 There are controversial studies regarding this matter. According recent contributions, the
10 presence of natural organic matter [12, 27] in real WW favor the disinfection
11 performance of photo-Fenton, which was explained by the authors as an accelerating
12 effect of natural photosensitizers. On the other hand, other articles show a clear
13 detrimental effect of organic matter content on the disinfection efficiency [17, 28],
14 attributed to a competence phenomenon between organic compounds and
15 microorganisms. This study adds more experimental evidences of the capability of solar
16 AOPs for real wastewater disinfection, highlighting also the unfavorable effect of organic
17 content.

18 19 **4. Conclusions**

- 20 • Our results demonstrate that the application of solar AOPs for water disinfection and
21 further reuse in agriculture may be an efficient practice.
- 22 • Different disinfection efficiency results observed for ferrous sulphate and ferric
23 nitrate clearly show that iron speciation in water is a key factor in photo-Fenton;
24 moreover Fe^{2+} was found to be the best option for *Fusarium* removal although, DOC
25 reduction was unaffected by this.
- 26 • Some differences in disinfection efficiency were observed between iron (5 and
27 10 mg/L) and H_2O_2 (10 and 20 mg/L) concentrations. The best disinfection result
28 was observed at 10/20 mg/L of $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ with periodic adding H_2O_2 .
- 29 • Experimental testing of these solar AOPs in synthetic and real urban WW effluents
30 led to similar inactivation times to attain the detection limit. In all cases (synthetic

1 and real), the treatments lasted less than three hours to reduce the *Fusarium* load to
2 the detection limit.

- 3 • The 60-L CPC solar reactor used in this study showed that this technology is a
4 promising option for wastewater disinfection in the presence of resistant water
5 microorganisms.

6

7 **5. Acknowledgements**

8 The authors wish to thank the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation for
9 funding received under the AQUASUN Project (Reference: CTM2011-29143-C03-03).

10

11 **6. References**

- 12 [1] P. Drechsel, C.A. Scott, L. Raschid-Sally, M. Redwood, A. Bahri, Wastewater
13 Irrigation and Health. Assessing and Mitigating Risk in Low-Income Countries,
14 ISBN 978-1-84407-795-3, 2010.
- 15 [2] FAO Statistical Yearbook, FAO Electronic Publishing, Food and Agriculture
16 Organization of the United Nations, Rome, 2006, p. 55.
- 17 [3] W.H. Schnitzler, Workshop on Non-chemical Alternatives to Replace Methyl
18 Bromide as a Soil Fumigant, in: R. Labraba (Ed.), ISBN 978-92-5-106001-8,
19 FAO Publishing Rome, 2008, pp. 61-69.
- 20 [4] T.M. Ayres, D.D. Mara, Analysis of Wastewater for Use in Agriculture -A
21 Laboratory Manual of Parasitological and Bacteriological Techniques,
22 Department of Civil Engineering, University of Leeds. Leeds, England World
23 Health Organization, Geneva, 1996.
- 24 [5] WHO, International Programme on Chemical Safety (IPCS), Disinfectants and
25 disinfectant by-products, International Program on Chemical Safety
26 (Environmental Health Criteria 216), Geneva, 1999.
- 27 [6] S. Malato, P. Fernández-Ibáñez, M.I. Maldonado, J. Blanco, W. Gernjak,
28 Decontamination and disinfection of water by solar photocatalysis: Recent
29 overview and trends, *Cat. Today*. 147 (2009) 1–59.
- 30 [7] V. Augugliaro, M. Litter, L. Palmisano, J. Soria, The combination of
31 heterogeneous photocatalysis with chemical and physical operations: a tool for

- 1 improving the photo-process performance, J Photochem Photobiol C: Photochem
2 Rev. 7 (2006) 127–144.
- 3 [8] P. Fernández-Ibáñez, C. Sichel, M.I. Polo-López, M. de Cara-García, J.C. Tello,
4 Photocatalytic disinfection of natural well water contaminated by *Fusarium solani*
5 using TiO₂ slurry in solar CPC photo-reactors, Cat. Today. 144 (2009) 62–68.
- 6 [9] C. Sichel, J. Tello, M. de Cara, P. Fernández-Ibáñez, Solar photocatalytic
7 disinfection of agricultural pathogenic fungi: *Fusarium* species. Appl. Cat. B:
8 Environ. 74 (2007) 152–160.
- 9 [10] M.I. Polo-López, P. Fernández-Ibáñez, I. García-Fernández, I. Oller, I. Salgado-
10 Tránsito, C. Sichel, Resistance of *Fusarium* sp spores to solar TiO₂
11 photocatalysis: influence of spore type and water (scaling-up results), J. Chem.
12 Technol. Biotechnol. 85 (2010) 1038–1048.
- 13 [11] M.I. Polo-López, I. García-Fernández, I. Oller, P. Fernández-Ibáñez, Solar
14 disinfection of fungal spores in water aided by low concentrations of hydrogen
15 peroxide, Photochem. & Photobiol. Sci. 10 (2011) 381-388.
- 16 [12] D. Spuhler, J.A. Rengifo-Herrera, C. Pulgarín, The effect of Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺, H₂O₂ and
17 the photo-Fenton reagent at near neutral pH on the solar disinfection (SODIS) at
18 low temperatures of water containing *Escherichia coli* K12, Appl. Cat B: Environ.
19 96 (2010) 126-141.
- 20 [13] I. García-Fernández, M.I. Polo-López, I. Oller, P. Fernández-Ibáñez, Bacteria and
21 fungi inactivation using Fe³⁺/sunlight, H₂O₂/sunlight and near neutral photo-
22 Fenton: A comparative study, App. Cat. B: Environ. 121-122 (2012) 20-29.
- 23 [14] M.R. Hoffmann, S.T. Martín, W. Choi, D. Bahnemann, Environmental
24 applications of semiconductor photocatalysis, Chem. Rev. 95 (1995) 69-78.
- 25 [15] E. Pignatello, A. Oliveros, McKay, Advanced oxidation processes for organic
26 contaminant destruction based on the Fenton reaction and related chemistry, Crit.
27 Rev. in Environ. Sci. and Tech. 36 (2006) 1-84.
- 28 [16] C. Sichel, P. Fernández-Ibáñez, M. de Cara, J. Tello, Lethal synergy of solar UV-
29 radiation and H₂O₂ on wild *Fusarium solani* spores in distilled and natural well
30 water, Wat. Res. 43 (2009) 1841-1850.

- 1 [17] M.I. Polo-López, I. García-Fernández, T. Velegraki, A. Katsoni, I. Oller, D.
2 Mantzavinos, P. Fernández-Ibáñez, Mild solar photo-Fenton: An effective tool for
3 the removal of *Fusarium* from simulated municipal effluents, Appl. Catal. B:
4 Environ. 111-112 (2012) 545-554.
- 5 [18] C.W. Jones, Applications of hydrogen peroxide and derivatives. James H. Clark
6 (Ed). Royal Society of chemistry, Cambridge, UK, ISBN 0-85404-536-8, 1999,
7 264 pp.
- 8 [19] F. Sciacca, J.A. Rengifo-Herrera, J. Wéthé, C. Pulgarin, Dramatic enhancement of
9 solar disinfection (SODIS) of wild *Salmonella* sp. in PET bottles by H₂O₂
10 addition on natural water of Burkina Faso containing dissolved iron, Chem. 78
11 (2010) 1186-1191.
- 12 [20] A. Markowska-Szczupaka, K. Ulfig, A.W. Morawski, The application of titanium
13 dioxide for deactivation of bioparticulates: An overview, Cat. Today. (2011).
14 Doi:10.1016/j.cattod.2010.11.055
- 15 [21] J. Kiwi, V. Nadtochenko, New Evidence for TiO₂ Photocatalysis during Bilayer
16 Lipid Peroxidation, J. Phys. Chem. B 108 (2004) 17675-17684.
- 17 [22] S. Canonica, T. Kohn, M. Mac, F.J. Real, J. Wirz, U. von Guten, Photosensitizer
18 method to determine rate constants for the reaction of carbonate radical with
19 organic compounds, Environ. Sci. Technol. 39 (2005) 9182.
- 20 [23] M.I. Polo-López, I. Oller, P. Fernández-Ibáñez, Benefits of photo-Fenton at low
21 concentrations for solar disinfection of distilled water. A case study:
22 *Phytophthora capsici*, Cat. Tod. 209 (2013) 181-187.
- 23 [24] J. De Laat, G. Truong Le, B. Kegube, A comparative study of the effects of
24 chloride, sulphate and nitrate ions on the rates of decomposition of H₂O₂ and
25 organic by Fe(II)/H₂O₂ and Fe(III)/H₂O₂, Chem. 55 (2004) 715-723.
- 26 [25] W. Gernjak, M. Fuerhacker, P. Fernández-Ibáñez, J. Blanco, S. Malato, Solar
27 photo-Fenton treatment – Process parameters and process control, Appl. Catal. B:
28 Environ. 64 (2006) 121-130.
- 29 [26] F. Bichai, M.I. Polo López, P. Fernández-Ibáñez, Solar disinfection of wastewater
30 to reduce contamination of lettuce crops by *E. coli* in reclaimed water irrigation,
31 Wat. Res. 4-6 (2012) 6040-6050.

- 1 [27] J. Rodríguez-Chueca, M.I. Polo-López, R. Mosteo, M.P. Ormad, P. Fernández-
2 Ibáñez. Disinfection of real and simulated urban wastewater effluents using a mild
3 solar photo-Fenton. *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental*, 150-151 (2014), 619-
4 629.
- 5 [28] E. Ortega-Gómez, M. Ballesteros Martín, B. Esteban García, J.A. Sánchez Pérez,
6 P. Fernández Ibáñez, Solar photo-Fenton for water disinfection: An investigation
7 of the competitive role of model organic matter for oxidative species. *Applied*
8 *Catalysis B: Environmental*, 148-149 (2014), 484-489.
9

1 **TABLE CAPTIONS**

2

3 **Table 1.** Concentration of Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} and total iron (Fe^{T}), initial and final, and pH for
4 different photo-Fenton reactions in distilled water (Figure 3).

5

6 **Table 2.** Concentration of Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} and total iron (Fe^{T}), initial and final, and pH for
7 different photo-Fenton reactions in distilled water (Figures 4 and 5).

8

9 **Table 3.** *F. solani* inactivation kinetics constants.

10

1 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

2

3 **Figure 1.** Photograph of the CPC photo-reactor used in this work (a). Solar UVA and
4 spectral irradiance distribution at PSA (Spain) during one of the days of experiment (b).

5

6 **Figure 2.** *F. solani* inactivation in CPC reactor under sunlight and 10 mg/L H₂O₂ in DW
7 and SMWWE.

8

9 **Figure 3.** *F. solani* inactivation in CPC reactor with solar photocatalysis (100 mg/L of
10 TiO₂) in SMWWE.

11

12 **Figure 4.** *F. solani* inactivation kinetics in CPC reactor using photo-Fenton at different
13 ratios of Fe²⁺/H₂O₂ (a) and Fe³⁺/H₂O₂ (b) in distilled water.

14

15 **Figure 5.** *F. solani* inactivation in CPC reactor using photo-Fenton with ferrous sulphate
16 in SMWWE at several concentrations (a), DOC reduction during same experiments (b).

17

18 **Figure 6.** *F. solani* inactivation in CPC reactor using photo-Fenton with ferric nitrate in
19 SMWWE at pH3 and several reagent concentrations (a), DOC removal during same
20 experiments (b).

21

22 **Figure 7.** Inactivation profile of *F. solani* (a) and other naturally present fungi (b) in CPC
23 reactor using solar photo-Fenton (ferrous sulphate, pH3), TiO₂, and H₂O₂ in real effluents
24 of MWWE.

25

1 **Table 1**

2

	Fe/H₂O₂	Fe²⁺_i/Fe²⁺_f	Fe³⁺_i/Fe³⁺_f	Fe^T_i/Fe^T_f	pH
Fe²⁺-Photo-Fenton (Fig. 3a)					
(-■-)	5/10	0.8/1.2	2.1/1.1	2.9/2.4	4.8
(-●-)	5/10(+10)*	0.8/1.0	2.8/1.6	3.7/2.6	5.4
(-▲-)	10/20	0.0/1.2	8.4/0.4	8.4/1.6	6.4
Fe³⁺-Photo-Fenton (Fig. 3b)					
(-■-)	5/10	0.2/1.1	4.5/0.7	4.7/1.9	5.2
(-▲-)	10/20	0.4/1.8	6.9/0.8	7.2/2.7	5.0

3

*Experiment with H₂O₂ dosage

1 **Table 2**

2

	Fe/H₂O₂	addition of H₂O₂ during experim.	Fe²⁺_i/Fe²⁺_f	Fe³⁺_i/Fe³⁺_f	Fe^T_i/Fe^T_f	pH
Fe²⁺-Photo-Fenton (Fig. 4)						
(-■-)	5/10	-	-	-	-	8.0
(-●-)	5/10	-	0.7/0.7	2.9/2.1	3.6/2.8	3.0
(-▲-)	5/50*	4 x 10 mg/L	1.0/0.5	2.9/0.6	3.9/1.2	3.3
(-◆-)	10/20	-	1.7/2.2	6.6/4.3	8.4/6.6	3.0
(-▼-)	10/20*	4 x 20 mg/L	1.6/1.9	6.2/3.7	7.8/5.7	3.0
Fe³⁺-Photo-Fenton (Fig. 5)						
(-■-)	5/10	-	0.5/1.5	4.6/3.5	5.1/4.9	3.1
(-●-)	5/10*	6 x 10 mg/L	0.4/1.1	3.6/2.3	4.0/3.4	3.1
(-▲-)	10/20	-	0.6/2.5	7.7/4.9	8.4/7.5	3.0
(-▼-)	10/20*	6 x 20 mg/L	0.2/1.1	6.1/6.3	8.2/7.4	3.0

3

4

*Experiments with H₂O₂ dosage

1 **Table 3**

Solar treatment	Fe (mg/L)	H ₂ O ₂ (mg/L)	<i>k</i> (L/kJ)	R ²	Kinetic model
H ₂ O ₂ (<i>Fig. 1</i>)	-	10	0.10±0.02	0.95	Log-linear
TiO ₂ (<i>Fig. 2</i>)	-	-	0.07±0.01	0.95	Log-linear
Fe²⁺-Photo-Fenton (<i>Fig. 4a</i>)					
	5 (pH8)	10	0.01±0.00	0.99	Log-linear
	5	10	0.10±0.03	0.95	Log-linear
	5	10+40*	0.17±0.02	0.98	Log-linear
	10	20	0.10±0.01	0.98	Log-linear
	10	20+80*	0.30±0.10	0.93	Log-linear
Fe³⁺-Photo-Fenton (<i>Fig. 5a</i>)					
	5	10	0.10±0.01	0.98	Log-linear
	5	10+60*	0.14±0.01	0.99	Log-linear
	10	20	0.12±0.01	0.99	Log-linear
	10	20+120*	0.14±0.03	0.95	Log-linear

2 *Experiments with H₂O₂ dosage

1 **Figure 1**

2

3

(a)

4

5

(b)

1
2

Figure 2

3

1 Figure 3

2

3

1 Figure 4

2

3

a)

4

b)

1 Figure 5

2

3

a)

4

b)

1 **Figure 6**

2

3

a)

4

b)

5

1 Figure 7

2

a)

3

b)